

Capital markets and stocks that pay dividends

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to identify whether the level of knowledge people on the capital market interferes in the process of making an investment decision. The Brazilian stock market is proving a new phase, mainly due to the pension reform that expanded the retirement age, the lower basic interest rate of the historical series, which was 5% per year in November 2019 and the announcement of privatizations in the sectors of infrastructure, these events contributed to the Stock Market 'B3' to reach 108,290 points in November 2019, the largest historic brand. In this study, two hypotheses were formulated, and H_0 = rejects that the level of knowledge on the market of variable income changes to decision-making, H_1 = It is accepted that the level of knowledge on the market of variable income changes to decision-making. To collect the information, it was applied a questionnaire with closed questions 5. Were obtained 273 valid responses. We applied the test of Pearson's Chi-squared test with a significance level of 5%. After this, in questions 4 and 5, it was applied the annotated paraconsistent logic to analyze the heuristic process of decision-making, confirming or denying the hypotheses. The results indicate that the level of knowledge interferes in decision-making and investors with a good level of understanding of the market, invest in shares of companies, since investors with regular understanding or who do not know, are in the field of doubt, indicating that do not invest with frequency or simply do not invest in shares.

Keywords: Pay-Out. Dividend Yield. Dividends, Capital Market, Actions

I. INTRODUCTION

The capital market is a securities distribution system that provides liquidity to securities issued by companies and facilitates the process of capitalization. It is constituted by the stock exchanges, brokerage firms and other financial institutions authorized. In the case of Brazil, the main stock is the "B3".

There are several changes in the Brazilian scenario, which stimulated investment in the stock market, among them, there is the reform of the social security which increased the age and the time of contribution (Brazil, 2019), the sharp fall in the rate of interest that represented the lowest historical value, is currently at the level of 5%.

The Brazilian stock market witnessed a low dynamism in recent years, as determined by the excess of physical assets that served as collateral for financing by providing a reduction in interest rates, the tax allowances, renegotiation of tax debts and the cultural aspects of investors (Perobelli, 2007).

With the sharp fall in interest rates and the low yield of fixed income options, the B3, reached 108,290 points on 28 November 2019. In the stock market there are several strategies for acquisition of shares, among them we can mention stocks that pay dividends or not. In the case of Warren Buffet his preference is for actions that do not pay dividends (Schroeder, 2008). As for the largest invested of B3 in Brazil, the preference is for stocks that pay dividends (PGN, 2019). The dividends represent an income in a given period, which depending on the rate of income tax may lead investors to opt for actions that do not pay dividends, while investors with an exemption or rates of income tax minors may prefer stocks that pay dividends, is the clientele effect (Miller & Modigliani, 1961). In the Brazilian capital market in the period from 1998 to 2010, it was observed that this effect (Holland & Coelho, 2012).

The objective of this article was to identify whether the level of knowledge of the people about actions interferes in the decision-making process. Being determined two hypotheses H_0 = rejects that the level of knowledge on the market of variable income changes to decision-making, H_1 = It is accepted that the level of knowledge on the market of variable income changes the decision-making process. To collect the information, fhi applied a questionnaire containing 5 closed questions, being obtained 273 valid responses. Were applied to the test of Pearson's Chi-squared test, with a confidence index of 95% to confirm or deny the hypothesis. After this, in questions 4 and 5, it was applied the annotated

paraconsistent logic to analyze the heuristic process of decision-making, confirming or denying the hypotheses. The results indicate that the level of knowledge interferes in decision-making and investments with a good level of understanding of the market, invest in the stock market, since investors with regular understanding or who do not know, are in the field of doubt, indicating that do not invest or not invest with frequency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

Several factors have led to a demand for greater understanding of the capital market as a source of income and investment, cites the pension reform in 2019, which established a minimum age for retirement of 65 years for men and 62 years for women, in addition to other changes such as the increase in time to reach 100% of the benefit, for women 35 years of contribution and for men 40 years of contributions (Brazil, 2019). Beyond the ceiling of retirement that is currently R\$ 5,839.45 reais. Joins this factor to reduction in the Selic rate, which is the basic interest rate of the economy that has reached the lowest level history of 5 % per year in October 2019. This makes the remuneration of investments in fixed income and savings are even smaller.

This range of reduction of basic interest rate, pension reform and privatization, there was a movement in the Bolsa de Valores de São Paulo "B3", where the Ibovespa index, formed by shares with highest volume traded, altered level, going from 51,992 points on 5 December 2014 to 108,290 points on 28 November 2019.

Many of the obstacles observed for the provision of capital market were related to structural aspects of businesses, such as the large volume of tangible assets that serve as collateral for loans by reducing the interest rate, financing of large corporations with resources from public bodies, the cultural aspect of the Brazilian not to invest in equities, the competitive aspect of certain markets. From the point of view of low dynamism of the capital market, are the direct and indirect costs with emissions and the lack of protection of minority shareholders (Perobelli, 2007).

This low market dynamism is not based on the behavioral aspects of the investor, as conservatism, confidence, trial, heuristic models of decision-making. These behaviors do not alter the price of shares in Brazil, not affecting the markets (Kimura, 2003).

The main securities traded (Furniture) represent the social capital of companies, implemented in their actions or even loans taken by companies in the market, represented by debentures that are convertible into shares, subscription bonuses and other commercial paper. This constitution allows the movement of capital and provides the economic development. The capital market can still be traded the rights and receipts of subscription of securities, certificates of deposits of shares and other derivatives authorized to trading (Assaf Neto, 2018). They can also be understood as a transfer of resources between agents with multiple advantages, on the one hand businesses need to capitalize on and on the other hand investors want return on investment (Perobelli, 2007).

The actions are variable income securities issued by corporations, which represent a smaller fraction of the capital of the issuer company. Can be collateral or represented by certificates or certificates (Brazil, 1976). The investor in shares is a coproprietor anonymous society of which it is a shareholder, participating in their results. The shares are convertible into cash, at any time, by trading on stock exchanges or over-the-counter market.

There are stocks that pay dividends, which represent a portion of the profit calculated by an anonymous society, distributed to shareholders on the closure of the fiscal year (Brazil, 1976).

The dividend policy it is a decision on the proportion of the net results within a specified period to be distributed to shareholders or to be reinvested in the company's activities. All shareholders are entitled to receive dividends in the same proportion in which they participate in the capital, barring a few exceptions, such as for example: a person who holds shares representing 10% of the capital, will receive 10% of the total profits of the company. The same company can belong to different categories and confer different rights as to dividends (Assaf Neto, 2018).

The change in the price actions have association with the dividend policy. The stock market in the United Kingdom was found a positive relationship between dividend yield and changes in stock price and a negative relation between the rate of payment of dividends and changes in stock price, concluding that the dividend policies are important to determine the price of shares (Hussainey, Oscar Mgbame, & Chijoke-Mgbame, 2011).

The world's largest investor Warren Buffet says that between their preferred shares are not those that pay dividends (Schroeder, 2008). Among its principles, this choosing the right job, not all segments are good; delegate

authority, respect the culture of the company, discovering competent persons, the delegation may not plastering work of people, among others; find the right administrator, who must have obsession with work, agree and think at work, honesty, long-term vision, motivation of staff and others, and finally, to motivate people, praise, be careful with the criticisms. This indicates that the type of investment focuses on the long term (Buffet & Clark, 2009).

However, even if there is no preference for actions that guarantee the shareholding in companies, which is a characteristic of the group Berkshire Hathaway Inc of Warren Buffet, in 2018 the group received US\$ 3.8 billion in dividends, being the main companies, American Express \$ 237 million, Apple \$ 745 million, Bank of America U\$ 551 million, Coca-Cola U\$ 624 million and Wells Fargo U\$ 809 million (Hathaway, 2018).

In Brazil, the largest investor, Luis Barsi, says that "money serves to make more money." The Paulistano for 80 years is not concerned with the oscillations of the Grant: your wager is in shares that pay good dividends (PGN, 2019).

Companies that pay dividends if use of various instruments in the conduct of their dividend policies, the most common being: distribution of dividends; splitting; repurchase of shares; reinvestment of profits and reinvestment of dividends (Assaf Neto, 2018).

There are several factors that influence a dividend policy: liquidity, growth perspective, considerations of the owners, legal restrictions on contracts of bonds or loans and market assessment. In Brazil in the period from 1998 to 2010, it was observed that the dividend policy confirms partially the clientele effect. (Holland & Coelho, 2012). This fact demonstrates that shareholders are subject to income tax rates higher, prefer to companies that do not pay dividends. In this way, would have as a group of shareholders, people who were not affected by the income tax, such as exemptions or lower rates (Miller & Modigliani, 1961).

Another aspect related to dividend policy is in the dissemination of information of dividends that reveal the level of conflict existing in the company between minority and majority shareholders, indicating that the presence of more than one shareholder with a shareholding, reveals the best levels of corporate governance, but it is still necessary to protect the rights of minority shareholders (Gugler & Yurtoglu, 2003).

There are three policies of dividends, the dividend policy with distributing content constant; the regular dividend policy and the policy of regular dividends more beds. There is not one that is the most indicated, being its uses dependent on each case and the strategies of the company (Assaf Neto, 2018).

The open capital companies, normally, distribute to its shareholders a portion of the profit in the form of dividends or interest on own capital (JCP). This payment is proportional to the quantity of shares held.

II.1 DIVIDEND YIELD AND PAY-OUT

Dividend Yield, abbreviated DY, or just Yield, is an English expression that translated literally means the dividend yield. It is an index designed to measure the profitability of dividends from a company in relation to the price of its shares. This index brings the benefit of being able to compare the profitability of dividends between companies. Is the ratio that corresponds to a fraction in which are listed in the numerator of the dividends per share and in the denominator unit price of the shares. He expresses, therefore, a part of the remuneration of shareholders.

$$\text{Yield ou DY} = \frac{D}{A} \quad (\text{I})$$

DY = Dividend yield in history (%).

D = value of the dividend of an exercise in R\$.

The = Price per share at the beginning of the year in R\$.

PAY-OUT means index of payment of dividends. Is the fraction of the net profit that a company paid to shareholders in dividends:

$$\text{PAYOUT} = \frac{DT}{LLA} \quad (\text{II})$$

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Payout index = dividend payments in %

DT = total value of dividend paid in an exercise in R\$.

LLA= adjusted net profit of R\$

The part of the earnings not paid to investors is left for the investment to offer the future growth of earnings, he open capital

III. RESEARCH METHODS

In this study uses three steps, the first one is related to the calculation of the sample, the second deals with the formulation of hypotheses to analyze the level of significance between the knowledge of people on the market of variable income with the decision on the investment, and finally the third observed the frequency of these investments.

The sample size was calculated using the software G*Power 3.1.9.4, using the average size of effect of 0.25, error of 5%, the sample size was 249 respondents, as shown in figure 1.

F tests – ANOVA: Fixed Effects, omnibus, one-way		
Analysis:	A priori: Compute required sample size	
Input:	Effect size f	= 0.25
	A err prob	= 0.05
	Power (1-β err prob)	= 0.95
	Number of groups	= 3
Output:	Noncentrality parameter λ	= 0.0000000
	Critical F	= 3.0320649
	Numerator df	= 2
	Denominator df	= 249
	Total sample size	= 252
	Current power	= 0.9514888

Figure 1: Sample size calculation a priori

Source: The Authors

The questionnaire was answered by 302 people, being considered 273 valid responses. The power after the collection of the information was 0.96 (0.95 a priori), as shown in Figure 2.

F tests – ANOVA: Fixed Effects, omnibus, one-way		
Analysis:	Post hoc: Compute achieved power	
Input:	Effect size f	= 0.25
	A err prob	= 0.05
	Total sample size	= 273
	Number of groups	= 3
Output:	Noncentrality parameter λ	= 17.0625000
	Critical F	= 3.0292181
	Numerator df	= 2
	Denominator df	= 270
	Power (1-β err prob)	= 0.9655312

Figure 2: Sample size calculation Verification

Source: The authors

The questionnaire presented 5 issues, technique widely used in the social sciences (GIL, 2008), the questionnaire should examine future issues, think beyond the present moment (Hill & Hill, 1998). The first question refers to the level of knowledge of shares traded on the Stock Exchange, separating in good, regular or don't know. The second question was asked whether to invest in the Stock Market. In the third question if you invest in stocks that pay dividends. The fourth issue is exposed to exploitation of the Company's shares Magazine Luiza in the period from 2017 to 2019, reinforcing the uncertainty in 2017 and asks if you invest in shares in the year 2019. The fifth question cites the same case of company Magazine Luiza and questions if you do not invest in shares in the year 2019.

To examine the statistical significance, which refers to the probability of rejecting the hypothesis, we used the index of 5% which is widely accepted and recommended (Hair Jr., Anderson, Tatham, & Black, 2005).

For this study were formulated two hypotheses:

H0 = rejects that the level of knowledge on the market of variable income amends the decision

H1 = It is accepted that the level of knowledge on the market of variable income changes to decision-making.

To examine the p.value, we used the R software, using the test of Pearson's Chi-squared test. To calculate the exact distribution, it was used the Monte Carlo method, because it is random sampling. To display the distribution with precision, the number should be large enough (Ratick & Schwarz, 2009). In the study were used 5000 samples.

The tests were applied in two rounds. At first, it was considered that the level of knowledge of the stock market with the decision on the investment. In the second, it was considered that the level of knowledge of the stock market with the decision of investments in stocks that pay dividends.

Confirming the intentionality in investing in variable income market was applied the evidential paraconsistent annotated method, which involves many aspects of fuzzy logic. This can be seen from various angles (Abe, Jair Minoro; Costa, 1992). The logic E_{τ} associated to each proposition p , in common sense, a constant annotation consisting of a pair $(\mu;\lambda)$, representing the following way: $p()$, μ $\mu;\lambda$ And λ vary in real closed interval $[0,1]$. Therefore, the pair $(\mu;\lambda)$ belongs to the cartesian product $[0,1] \times [0,1]$. Intuitively, μ represents the degree of evidence in favor expressed in p , and λ , the degree of evidence contrary expressed in p .

The operator Max of Reticulated $[0,1] \times [0,1]$, associated with the logic E_{τ} , is to be applied to a group of n annotations ($N \geq 1$). He acts so as to maximize the degree of certainty ($G_{cert} = \mu - \lambda$) of this group of annotations, selecting the best evidence favorable (largest value of μ) and the worst evidence contrary (lowest value of λ), not being applied in situations in which two or more items considered are not all determinants, simply that one of them has a favorable condition to consider satisfactory (Fabio Romeu de Carvalho; Jair Departamento de Risaralda Abe, 2011). It is defined as follows: $\text{Max} \{(\mu\lambda 1;1), (\mu\lambda 2;2), \dots, (\mu\nu;\nu) \lambda\} = (\max\{\mu\mu 1,2,\dots, n\} \mu ; \min\{\lambda\lambda 1,2,\dots,\lambda n\})$.

The operator of the RETICULATED MIN $[0,1] \times [0,1]$, associated with the logic E_{τ} , is to be applied to a group of n annotations ($N \geq 1$). He acts so as to minimize the degree of certainty ($G_{cert} = \mu - \lambda$) of this group of annotations, selecting the worst evidence favorable (lowest value of μ) and the best evidence contrary (largest value of λ), being applied in situations in which two or more items considered are all determinants, it is essential that all present favorable conditions to be considered the result of a satisfactory analysis (Fabio Romeu de Carvalho; Jair Departamento de Risaralda Abe, 2011). It is defined as follows: $\text{MIN} \{(\mu\lambda 1;1), (\mu\lambda 2;2), \dots, (\mu\nu;\nu) \lambda\} = (\min\{\mu\mu 1,2,\dots,n\} \mu ; \max\{\lambda\lambda 1,2,\dots,\lambda n\})$.

In the result, after application of the rules for maximizing and minimizing, adopts as limits of truth and falsehood as level of demand. In this way, there is evidence in favor or against the viability of acquisition of the asset, if there is a degree of certainty in module equal to or greater than 0.6. Summarized: $G_{cert} \geq 0.6 \rightarrow \text{Truth (V)}$, i.e., the acquisition of the asset is viable; $G_{cert} \leq -0,6 \rightarrow \text{falsehood (F)}$, i.e., the acquisition of the asset is impracticable; $0.6 < G_{cert} < 0.6 \rightarrow \text{Confused (T)}$, i.e., doubt, should be deepening of information.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the first round, it was examined whether the level of knowledge about the stock market influences the decision to invest or not. The results indicate that the p value was less than 0.05. To calculate the exact distribution, it was used the Monte Carlo method that also showed p. index value <0.05. This refutes the hypothesis H0 and accepts the hypothesis H1, indicating that the level of knowledge of the stock market determines the investment. In behavioral terms, a survey conducted with young university students, identified three profiles of investment being, totally open to change, the investor who believes in the future and the investor oriented toward values with security (Pinese, Moriguchi, & Pepper, 2015). Crowding these three profiles, it can be inferred that the young people are more concerned with the future, explaining in some way the large number of courses offered by brokerages and by their own B3. The Table 1 present the research data.

Table 1: Survey Data

Decision	Good	Don't Know	Adjust	Total
Yes	48	38	118	204
Do not		19	50	69
Total	48	57	168	273

Source: The Actors

In figure 3, show the calculations performed

Pearson's Chi-squared test

```
data: conhecimento
X-squared = 19.986, df = 2, p-value = 4.571e-05

> chisq.test(conhecimento,simulate.p.value=5000)
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Pearson's Chi-squared test with simulated p-value (based on 2000 replicates)

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data: conhecimento
X-squared = 19.986, df = NA, p-value = 0.0004998
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Figure 3: Pearson's chi-squared
Source: The Actors

In the second round, was realized the test of Pearson's Chi-squared test, considering the shares that pay dividends, the p value was less than 0.05. To confirm the exact distribution, it was used the Monte Carlo method with 5000 samples, p values were less than 0.05. Increasing the level of knowledge of the stock market, influence the decision to invest in this market. The table 2, present the data and calculations in figure 4.

Table 2: Data with decisions on actions with Dividends

Decision	Good	I don't know	Adjust	Overall total
Yes	48	26	141	215
Do not	0	31	27	58
	48	57	168	273

Source: The Actors

In figure 4, show the calculations performed

Pearson's Chi-squared test

data: conhecimento

X-squared = 53.052, df = 2, p-value = 3.019e-12

> chisq.test(konhecimento,simulate.p.value=5000)

Pearson's Chi-squared test with simulated p-value (based on 2000 replicates)

data: conhecimento

X-squared = 53.052, df = NA, p-value = 0.0004998

Figure 4: Pearson's chi squared Simulate 5000 value

Source: The authors

The ignorance of the stock market makes people opt for other forms, in search of safety by unaware that there are several companies that provide security and monthly income above the current options for investment. To reinforce this thesis, we evaluated the ticker GOAU4 company Gerdau. The metallurgic Gerdau S.A. is a Brazilian company of shareholdings, holding a share of control in the Gerdau S.A., one of the largest Brazilian companies and worldwide in the production and commercial exploitation of products of iron, steel and other metals.

Its area of operation covers several countries such as Argentina, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Spain, United States, Mexico, India, Peru, Dominican Republic, Uruguay and Venezuela. The metallurgic Gerdau S.A. and Gerdau S.A. will pay dividends and/or interest on equity equivalent to at least 30% of adjusted net profit of the financial year, determined in accordance with the Brazilian accounting practices. From 31 March 2003, the Gerdau companies realize the payment of dividends and/or interest on own capital on a quarterly basis as anticipation of the mandatory minimum dividend. The table 3, show payout and yield from Gerdau.

Table 3: Payout and Yield - distribution of dividends (R\$ million)

Gerdau S.A.	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Adjusted Net Profit - LLA (Basis for dividends) *	1,863	1,292	1,435	1,282	(4,551)	(2,891)	(359)	2,171
Deliberate Dividends - DT	597	408	477	426	253	85	136	765
<i>Pay-out</i>	32.0%	31.6%	33.2%	33.2%	-	-	-	35.2%
<i>Yield</i> **	1.5%	1.7%	1.6%	1.4%	1.6%	1.1%	0.7%	3.6%
The historical value of the action in specific date	23-12 R\$ 18.24	22-12 R\$ 22.38	22-12 R\$ 23.61	22-12 R\$ 11.42	22-12 R\$ 1.45	22-12 R\$ 4.54	22-12 R\$ 5.72	22-12 R\$ 6.80

Source: GERDAU (2019)

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* Explanatory Note of net worth.

** historical Dividends paid per share exercise / historical value of the action.

According to table 3, the calculation was Payout of Gerdau.

$$Payout = \frac{DT}{LLA} \quad (III)$$

$$\text{Pay-out (2011)} = \frac{597}{1.863} = 0.320450 \text{ or } 32.0\%$$

$$\text{Pay-out (2012)} = \frac{408}{1292} = 0.31578 \text{ or } 31.6\%$$

$$\text{Pay-out (2013)} = \frac{477}{1.435} = 0.33240 \text{ or } 33.2\%$$

$$\text{Pay-out (2014)} = \frac{426}{1.282} = 0.33229 \text{ or } 33.2\%$$

$$\text{Pay-out (2018)} = \frac{765}{2.171} = 0.35237 \text{ or } 35.2\%$$

For example, the company of Gerdau S.A., approved the distribution of dividends to its shareholders, the value of R\$0.2448 per share, to be paid on 30/12/2018. Projecting the price of shares of GOAU4 R\$6.80 at the end of the financial year 2018, will calculate the dividend yield in the following way:

$$DY = \frac{D}{A} \quad (IV)$$

DY = Dividend yield (%).

D = value of the dividend of an exercise in R\$.

The = Price per share at the beginning of the year in R\$.

$$DY = \frac{0,2448}{6,80} = DY = 0,036 \text{ ou } 3,6\%$$

In the above example the GOAU4, pay 3.6% on the value of the action at the end of 2018.

In addition to the dividends, the companies also pay through Interest on Equity (JSCP). Projecting the price of shares GOAU4 toward the end of 2019 at R\$ 6.80, the same values of dividends and if she also pay a projected value of R\$0.44 per share of jscp, with 15% of the income tax withheld at source (R\$0.07), i.e., R\$0.37 per share of net profit.

$$DY = (0,2448 + 0,37) / 6,80$$

$$DY = 0,13894 \text{ ou } 13,89\%$$

In the above example the GOAU4 pay 13.89% on the value of the final action in 2019. In addition to the dividends, the companies also pay through Interest on Equity (JSCP). In the example, GOAU4 also paid R\$0.44 per share of jscp, with 15% of the income tax withheld at source (R\$0.07), i.e., R\$0.37 per share of net profit. Figure 5 presents the set of actions that most paid dividends in 2019.

Name	Part	Subsector	Yield % (12 months)	Yield + Jcp % (12 months)
Petrobras	Brst3	Oil	13.58	13.58
Cyrela	CYRE3	Construction	4.86	12.89
Banco do Brasil	BBSE3	Social Security	6.92	11.87
Itau	ITUB4	Banks	6.46	9.75
Cielo	CIEL3	Financial	4.11	9.62
Yduqs	YDUQ3	Education	4.58	8.57
Qualicorp	What3	Health	5.12	8.51

Figure 5: largest dividend payers in in 2019
Source: Rico (2019)

In table 1 it is possible to observe that the brst3 paid 13.58% Yield + JCP, as well as 12.89% CYRE3 BBSE3 11.87%, 9.75% ITUB4, CIEL3 9.62%, 8.57% and YDUQ3 which 8.51%, respectively. In tax matters there are differences between dividends and JCP, to receive dividends the value already nets of income tax, which is taxed at source, the JCP already paying the tax is paid at a rate of 15% on the value received.

Of course, that this work, there is a recommendation on investments, but only on the considerations about the theme of the stock market and it has grown significantly, raising the Ibovespa index to the largest historic value in the house of 108 thousand points.

To distort the hypotheses, was adopted to paraconsistent logic notes highlights Et, were separated into three groups, Group 1 is formed by people with good knowledge in the stock market, the Group 2, formed by people with reasonable knowledge and the Group 3, formed by people who do not know. Figure 6 presents the results.

Group 1			Group 2			Group 3			Between Groups			
Good			Reasonable			Don't Know						
μ_{max}	λ_{min}	Gcert _{in group}	μ_{max}	λ_{min}	Gcert _{in group}	μ_{max}	λ_{min}	Gcert _{in group}	μ_{min}	$\lambda_{\epsilon_{max}}$	Gcert	Decision
1	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.4	0.4	Doubt

Figure 6: level of knowledge and the degree of certainty or uncertainty
Source: The Actors

The group 1, is among those who invest in the stock market, since the groups 2 and 3, generated doubt. Reinforcing the previous tests that the level of knowledge is related decision in investing in shares or not.

V. CONCLUSION

The objective of this work was to identify whether the level of knowledge of the people about income variable influences the decision of investment.

We collected 273 valid responses, the p.value, investment in shares and investment in stocks that pay dividends, were smaller 0.05, in order to obtain a perfect distribution 5000 sampling were performed using the Monte Carlo method, which confirmed the hypothesis that the level of knowledge of the market, influence on decision-making and investments.

The cultural aspects and the successive government subsidies impact on discouraged of enterprises in seeking resources on the capital market. With the change of economic policy in the market reached new heights, accumulates to this the weak economic growth in the last 8 years, which led companies to seek resources on the capital market.

We calculated the dividend yield and payout of shares GOAU4. It has been noted that in a projection of the same for 2019 can be paid 13.89% on the value of each action. In addition to the dividends, the companies also pay through Interest on Own Capital (JCP). In the study, GOAU4 also paid R\$0.44 per share of JCP, with 15% of the income tax

withheld at source (R\$0.07), i.e., R\$0.37 per share of net profit. Another factor to highlight, is the historic profitability of shares, remunerating shareholders every year. In the same way that invests in fixed income, the income variable in companies with historical series represents lower risk than the culturally designed by people.

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